

Modern practice of hr-managers' psychological and pedagogical competence formation

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the study of the practice of HR managers' psychological and pedagogical competence formation in institutions of higher education. The analysis of these practices was carried out on the example of higher education institutions of Ukraine and China. The purpose of the article is to reveal the advantages and disadvantages of the formation of psychological and pedagogical competence of HR-managers in universities in order to understand their essence and, in future, to develop recommendations for their correction. The results of the analysis of the scientific and pedagogical literature, which presents the investigated problem from different perspectives, are highlighted. The analysis of regulatory documents in the sphere of higher education system functioning in Ukraine and China was performed. The educational programs of the first (bachelor's), second (master's) and third (educational and scientific) levels of higher education of the best universities of Ukraine and China were analyzed and their features were identified. The conducted analysis shows that the formation of psychological and pedagogical competence at the level of initial professional training of HR-managers is insufficient, is not systemic, aimed at the formation of its individual components, which justifies the need for its formation in the process of corporate training organization.

Keywords: HR manager, psychological and pedagogical competence, higher education institution, Ukraine, China, educational program.

Сучасна практика формування психолого-педагогічної компетентності HR-менеджерів

Анотація. Стаття присвячена дослідженню практики формування психолого-педагогічної компетентності HR-менеджерів у закладах вищої освіти. Аналіз такої практики виконано на прикладі закладів вищої освіти України та Китаю. Мета статті – виявити переваги і недоліки формування психолого-педагогічної компетентності HR-managers в університетах з задля розуміння їхньої сутності та в подальшому розробки рекомендацій щодо їх виправлення. Висвітлено результати аналізу науково-педагогічної літератури, що висвітлює досліджувану проблему з різних перспектив. Виконано аналіз нормативних документів, що регулюють функціонування системи вищої освіти в Україні та Китаї. Проаналізовано освітні програми першого (бакалаврського) другого (магістерського) та третього (освітньо-наукового) рівнів вищої освіти кращих університетів України та Китаю та виявлено такі особливості: розроблення, затвердження та застосування стандартів вищої освіти в практиці закладів вищої освіти;

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застосування механізмів централізації та децентралізації при розробці освітніх програм; підготовка майбутніх менеджерів за «Менеджмент», «Менеджмент організацій та адміністрування» (Україна), «Менеджмент та бізнес-адміністрування», «Менеджмент та публічне адміністрування» (Китай) з одночасною відсутністю спеціальних освітніх компонентів, які сприяють формуванню психолого-педагогічної компетентності HR-менеджерів; забезпечення освітніх програм за спеціальністю «HR-менеджмент» факультетами економіки та менеджменту (досвід України та Китаю), а також факультетами менеджменту та адміністрування, факультетами державного управління, факультетами соціальних наук (досвід Китаю); використання різноманітних механізмів формування окремих складових психолого-педагогічної компетентності майбутніх HR-менеджерів. Проведений аналіз показує, що сформованість психолого-педагогічної компетентності на рівні початкової професійної підготовки HR-менеджерів є недостатньою, не відрізняється системністю, спрямованою на формування окремих її компонентів, що обґрунтовує необхідність її формування у процесі організації корпоративного навчання.

Ключові слова: HR-менеджер, психолого-педагогічна компетентність, заклад вищої освіти, Україна, Китай, освітня програма.

Introduction

At the beginning of the 21st century, special attention is paid to the problem of personnel management, which is considered as a potential for the economic and social development of society. Currently, companies are interested in organizing corporate training, which is used as a tool for their own strategic development, development of the talents of their employees, formation of initiative, innovation and corporate culture in general. HR-managers are supposed to make their own contribution to the development of the company's human capital, and therefore need knowledge, skills and abilities that will contribute to the establishment of a constructive professional environment in the company. We consider psychological and pedagogical competence as a component of HR-managers' professional competence, which requires special research attention.

The analysis of recent research and publications. The problem of HR-managers training, peculiarities of their professional competence formation, features of their professional activity are highlighted in scientific publications of modern scientists in various countries. Researchers analyse the competency model of HR-managers [1; 2; 10], quality of higher education and its influence on HR-managers' training [3; 5], professional and transferable competences of HR-managers [4; 16; 17; 18], etc.

The formulation of article purpose. Understanding the importance of psychological and pedagogical competence as an important component of the professional competence of HR-managers, we decided to analyze the practice of HR-managers' psychological and pedagogical competence formation in higher education institutions of Ukraine and China. We believe that the results of the study will serve as a basis for understanding the advantages and disadvantages of this experience and developing recommendations for their correction.

Results

In the context of our study, the modern practice of HR-managers' psychological and pedagogical competence formation requires research. First of all, it is worth referring to the requirements declared in the documents of associations and organizations that are recognized at the international level as professional ones in the field of management. They work in the modern market, analyse the needs of companies in the field of HR-management, study their activities and understand the essence of HR-managers' professional functions. The confirmation of the logic and accuracy of this thesis can be found in the scientific literature. For

example, Kozhan suggests considering the problem from the perspective of determining the duties of a HR-manager. "The type of HR-manager is determined by the level of the position (HR director, HR-manager) with the corresponding complexity of work and responsibility; by areas (functions) of HR-management: personnel selection manager – recruiter; training and development manager; motivation manager; compensation and reward manager; project manager; HR specialist, etc." [17, 99]. There is no doubt that "paying attention to human resources and promoting their capabilities is one of the most important assets of organizations. Therefore, transformational and effective actions and activities in the field of human resource management will enable organizations to expand their core competencies closer to reality" [2].

Specifying the concept of "professional competence of a manager", Kolisnyk notes: "Our analysis provides grounds for understanding the essence of the professional competence of specialists in the field of management as a quality integrative characteristic of a specialist's personality, which determines his readiness and ability to use professional functions in the field of economic activity, making optimal decisions, using professional knowledge and previous experience to achieve the desired result through the possession of innovative technologies for the development of the economy and considering the peculiarities of the society, as well as personal responsibility for the decisions made" [18, 70].

Scientists claim that "there are different classifications of approaches and methods for determining competencies". Further researchers distinguish three approaches, which "can be introduced to determine competencies: a) Borrowing strategy, b) Borrowing and localization strategy, c) Strategy for creating a suitable model for oneself" [2]. "In another classification of competency model design approaches by Briscoe and Hall, the design of managers' competency model by different organizations was done with the aim of categorizing these approaches. They found that the use of competency models is a recent phenomenon in organizations that leads them to increase competitiveness by resorting to any means, including developing the performance of their managers" [2].

In our research, we refer to documents presented by two international organizations: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (United Kingdom) [1] and Society for Human Resource Management [10].

Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (United Kingdom) is a professional association of specialists in the field of personnel management. In 2018, CIPD presented "The profession map", which "sets the international benchmark for the people profession" [1]. The structure of "The profession map" includes the following components: purpose; core knowledge; core behaviours; specialist knowledge [1].

We agree with the statement, that "traditionally, the competency model is both an instrument of personnel management and a key element of organizational strategy; it includes a set of competences necessary for the successful performance of work and tasks in the organization, successful career growth, increasing competitiveness on the labour market, etc. Universal competency models can be created for specific jobs, teams, tasks, activities, and organizations" [4, 326].

According to CIPD, "The profession map" encompasses principles-led, evidence-based, outcomes-driven purpose [1].

It is worth mentioning that core knowledge, proposed by CIPD involves the following: "people practice (understanding people practice; law and regulation; workforce planning; skills and capabilities; performance management; wellbeing; equality, diversity and inclusion; flexible ways of working; enabling flexible ways of working); culture and behaviour (organization culture; systems thinking; behavioral science; ethics; learning approaches; facilitation, coaching, consulting; effective teams; enabling resilience; employee engagement; diverse employee voices); business acumen (organization strategy and issues; external landscape; business model; value creation; organization performance; financial literacy;

strategic planning; governance; supplier management: environmental sustainability; brand); evidence-based practice (evidence-based practice; analysis and problem solving; data and analytics; research; stakeholder insights; measuring impact); technology and people (people technologies; collaborative technologies; social media; technology-enabled practices; impact of technology); change (business cases; managing change; continuous improvement and innovation; change experience and engagement; change levers; project management)” [1].

In the context of our research, it is necessary to consider not only the knowledge, but also the skills that HR-managers should possess, as well as the values and attitudes that are the components of their professional competence and influence their behaviour and activities in the professional environment.

“The Profession Map” of CIPD doesn’t determine the skills of managers. But the analysis of “Core behaviours” makes it possible to define the core skills through the outlined behaviours: “ethical practice (ethical decisions, impact of decisions, ethics and law, transparency, integrity); professional courage and influence (courage, communication; stakeholder relationships, influencing approach, accountability); valuing people (purposeful work, humanity, developing others, supporting managers, enabling voice, promoting wellbeing); working inclusively (inclusivity, valuing diversity, building relationships, collaborative working, sharing knowledge, conflict resolution, psychological safety); commercial drive (commercial focus, customer focus, financial acumen, delivery focus, personal resilience); passion for learning (the wider people profession, new approaches, CPD, learning from feedback, self-awareness); insights focused (understanding issues, gaining evidence, evaluating evidence, innovation, identifying connections); situational decision-making (evidence-based decisions, decision-making, adaptability, evaluation decisions) [1].

The results of the analysis of this document indicate that the listed competences and areas of their application relate to all professions belonging to the “human-human” system.

There is one more document worth analysing. This is “The SHRM Body of Competency and Knowledge” of Society for Human Resource Management [10], which determines competences of HR-managers. It presents the competence model, which incorporates behavioural and technical competences.

The analysis of this model shows that among the behavioural competences SHRM distinguishes the following: “leadership & navigation, ethical practice, business acumen, relationship management, consultation, critical evaluation, global & cultural effectiveness, communication” [10]. The SHRM Competency model outlines HR Expertise or HR knowledge which is subdivided into several domains: “people with the functional areas of talent acquisition & retention, employee engagement, learning and development, total rewards; organization (functional areas: structure of the HR function, organizational effectiveness & development, workforce management, employee relations, technology and data); workforce (functional areas: HR in the global context, diversity & inclusion, risk management, corporate social responsibility, employment law & regulations); strategy (functional areas: business & HR strategy)” [10].

The requirements for the competences of HR-managers, declared in both documents, reflect the needs of the labour market and employers in the international context. Also, compliance of the professional competence of HR-managers with these requirements provides grounds for their certification [1; 10].

We agree with Ukrainian researchers that investments in human capital are investments aimed at improving the qualifications and abilities of personnel, they are expenditures on education, health, and mobility of the labour force from low-productive workplaces to more highly productive ones. Dubinsky notes that the components of the professional competence of a HR-managers are as following: professional knowledge, skills, professionalism, professional abilities and experience, increasing the level of manifestation of competences due to their

formation and development, accumulation of new professional knowledge and their use, professional thinking, etc. [16].

Regarding the experience of higher education institutions that train future HR-managers, it is worth analysing their educational programs and finding out how they meet the requirements of employers for the professional competence of HR-managers, taking into account the international, national and regional contexts.

In our research, it is important to analyse the experience of higher education institutions regarding the initial training of HR-managers, as well as the formation of their psychological and pedagogical competence. For example, we performed an analysis of educational programs of several universities of Ukraine and the People's Republic of China, which offer training programs for managers. We selected universities using national rankings. In particular, the selection of higher education institutions of Ukraine was made in accordance with the rating "Top-200 Ukraine 2023" [11]. In this ranking, the best universities of Ukraine occupy the following positions:

1. National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute"
2. Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv
3. V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University
4. Lviv Polytechnic National University
5. Ivan Franko National University of Lviv [11].

Among Chinese universities, we choose 5 universities that occupy the highest positions in the "2023 Chinese University Ranking" [13]:

1. Tsinghua University
2. Peking University
3. Zhejiang University
4. Shanghai Jiao Tong University
5. University of Science and Technology of China [13].

The listed universities offer bachelor's, master's and doctoral level programs for training managers, and experienced teachers are involved in the training of future specialists in the field of management. Among the offered programs, we singled out those that are of great interest for our research as well as are directly related to the training of HR-managers.

The National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute" offers the "Management and Business Administration" program of the first (bachelor's) level of higher education. Students have the opportunity to study the "HR-management" course. The analysis of the syllabus of "HR-management" course shows that only one topic is indirectly related to the pedagogical aspect of HR-manager's activity. It is Topic 10: "Management of the development process and personnel movement", according to which the problem of professional development of the company's employees is considered.

At the National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute" the program of the second (master's) level of higher education "Management and Business Administration" presupposes the mastering of "Modern technologies of HR-management" course. The analysis of the syllabus of this educational component shows that it involves mastering the basics of Psychology, but the pedagogical content is absent.

At the National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute", the program of the third (educational and scientific) level of higher education "Management" provides for the study of the "Actual problems of pedagogy of higher education" course, aimed at forming the teaching competence of Doctors of Philosophy and their preparation for work in a higher education institution.

At Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, students have the opportunity to choose the educational and professional program of the first (bachelor's) level of higher education "Management of organizations". According to the curriculum, students study the subject "HR-

management” during the 5th semester. The results of the analysis of the content of this course make it possible to formulate the conclusion that only one topic (Topic 11. Personnel motivation and system efficiency) in this subject partially reveals the psychological aspects of the work with personnel, and the development of pedagogical knowledge is not foreseen.

Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv offers an educational and professional program of the second (master’s) level of higher education “Management and Business Administration”, however, no educational component of this program involves the formation of psychological and pedagogical competence of a manager. The same applies to the educational and scientific program for the training of a Doctor of Philosophy. An exception is the educational component “Assistant Pedagogical Practice”.

The study of the experience of V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University shows that this institution of higher education of Ukraine offers an educational and professional program of the first (bachelor’s) level of higher education “HR-management”. The analysis of this program shows that the formation of psychological and pedagogical competence is provided by a number of educational components, including Psychology and pedagogy, HR-management, Personnel motivation an evaluation, Training and coaching technologies in HR-manager’s activity, Leadership and teamwork, as well as elective course Psychology of social interaction.

The educational and professional programs of the second (master’s) level of higher education “Management of organizations and administration”, “Management of organizations”, offered by V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, do not provide any course for the formation of psychological and pedagogical competence of future managers. Also, this institution of higher education does not offer an educational program for training Doctors of Philosophy in the field of “Management”.

According to the information posted on the website of Lviv Polytechnic National University, this institution of higher education offers first (bachelor’s), second (master’s) and the third (educational-scientific) level of higher education programs in the field of knowledge “Management”.

The Bachelor’s program “Management” allows students to choose several specializations, among which are “HR-management and administration”. The analysis of the program shows that such specialization is implemented through the study of a number of courses. In particular, future bachelors study HR-analytics, Personnel motivation, Leadership technologies in organization, Management of intellectual potential of organization, Psychology and social-legislative dialogue in management, Corporate culture, Management of personnel development in organization.

The master’s program “HR-management” provides the possibility to study such core educational components as Personnel recruiting and adaptation, Personnel learning and development, as well as elective courses: Personnel assessment and HR-analytics, Corporate culture and communication management, Talents management, Team management and transformative leadership, Employer brand and social responsibility, Conflict management.

Among the elective courses of the educational and scientific program “Management” for future Doctor of Philosophy, one can find such educational components as Communication management, Anticipative management, Modern concepts of human capital management, Socio-humanistic paradigm of management.

At Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, students can choose the bachelor’s program titled “Management of organizations and administration”. This program involves the study of courses, mastering knowledge which contributes to the formation of psychological and pedagogical competence: Psychology of management, Multicultural management, Self-management, Leadership and group dynamics, HR-management, Communication management. Among the elective courses one can find Business-training of professional success.

The program for the same specialty of the second (master's) level of higher education offers such core courses as Corporate management, Leadership psychology, Management consulting, as well as elective courses: Knowledge management, Modern technologies of HR-management, Strategic leadership in frame of changes, Corporate social responsibility, Management of communicative processes at the enterprise, Psychology of personnel selection.

The educational and scientific program of the third (educational and scientific) level of higher education "Management", which provides the possibility to study such courses as Methods of knowledge conceptualization, Pedagogy of higher education, Psychology of higher education, is worth mentioning in our study.

In Ukraine and China, the reform of higher education is underway, which is aimed at its modernization, standardization and harmonization with the trends of the international space of higher education [6]. Jing claims, that "Education Modernization 2035 in China" further proposes to improve the education quality standard system, and formulate education quality standards that cover the whole school sector, reflect the world's advanced level and meet the characteristics of different types of education at different levels. In 2018, the national standards for the class teaching of undergraduate course of common colleges and universities ", this is issued to the nation and the world's first national standards for higher education teaching, and the developing trend in the world attaches great importance to the talent training quality is consistent, the construction with Chinese characteristics, the level of higher education quality standards system has an important landmark significance" [3, 3].

In China, special attention is paid to ensuring the quality of higher education and developing standards for the training of bachelors, masters and doctors of philosophy [7].

It should be emphasized that higher education standards have been developed and approved in Ukraine for the training of bachelors, masters, and Doctors of Philosophy in the field of knowledge "Management". In the context of our research, it is worth analysing those general and professional competencies, which are considered as components of such an integrative concept as the psychological and pedagogical competence of a manager, in particular, an HR-manager.

For example, the standard of higher education of the first (bachelor's) level declares that managers should possess the following competencies:

"general: the ability to learn and master modern knowledge; valuing and respecting diversity and multiculturalism; the ability to act on the basis of ethical considerations (motives);

professional: the ability to act socially responsibly and consciously; the ability to work in a team and establish interpersonal interaction when solving professional tasks; the ability to evaluate the performed work, ensure the quality and motivate the organization's personnel; the ability to create and organize effective communications in the management process; understand the principles of psychology and use them in professional activities; the ability to form and demonstrate leadership qualities and behavioral skills" [19].

Regarding the standard of higher education of the second (master's) level in the field of "Management", it is declared here that masters are expected to be able to demonstrate the following competencies:

"general: the ability to communicate with representatives of other professional groups of different levels; the ability to motivate people and move towards a common goal; the ability to act on the basis of ethical considerations (motives);

professional: the ability to establish values, vision, mission, goals and criteria by which the organization determines further development directions, develop and implement appropriate strategies and plans; ability for self-development, lifelong learning and effective self-management; the ability to form leadership qualities and demonstrate them in the process

of managing people; the ability to use psychological technologies for working with personnel” [20].

Scientists claim, that many innovations and reforms have been introduced into the higher education of China. “A significant reform since the late 1990s has been the amalgamation of several higher education institutions to create strong, comprehensive universities. The principal goal is to achieve administrative, economic and academic benefits, by merging institutions into large units, based on the assumption that larger units would yield qualitatively stronger academic institutions and better management and use of administrative resources” [5, 60].

We agree that “higher education has entered the era of popularization in China. To adapt to the development of higher education globalization and internationalization, we should further deepen reform and innovation, and accelerate the construction and improvement of quality assurance, so we can effectively improve high education quality” [3, 4].

Nowadays, in Tsinghua University [12], Zhejiang University [15], Shanghai Jiao Tong University [9], University of Science and Technology of China [14] students are trained according to the “Management and business administration” educational program for bachelor degree, and “Management” program of master’s and PhD levels of higher education. Similar situation is in Peking University with the only difference in the bachelor’s program, which is called “Management and public administration” [8].

The analysis of educational programs of Chinese universities shows that the situation is similar to the experience of Ukraine. The list of disciplines that form the psychological and pedagogical competence of future managers is analogous in four out of five universities [8; 9; 12; 14; 15]. Here, programs of the first (bachelor) level of higher education offer such courses as Management, Modern enterprise management, HR-management, Organizational behaviour [8; 9; 12; 14; 15]. According to the educational program of Peking University, future bachelors study such courses as Public administration, Management psychology, Public administration, Public ethics, Science of leadership [8]. However, the educational programs of the second (master’s) and third (educational and scientific) level of doctors of philosophy training in all five universities do not provide individual courses in this direction [8; 9; 12; 14; 15].

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the experience of higher education institutions of Ukraine and China which offer programs in the field of knowledge “Management” and train future managers, as well as HR-managers, we confirm that this experience is characterized by the following features:

- the development, approval and application of higher education standards in the practice of higher education institutions for the first (bachelor’s), second (master’s), third (educational and scientific) levels of higher education;
- the application of the mechanisms of centralization of educational programs development (the development of university programs for the first (bachelor’s), second (master’s), third (educational and scientific) level of higher education is implemented in accordance with state standards of higher education) and decentralization (using the right of autonomy, modern universities are independent in the formation of educational programs’ content) in educational programs development;
- the training of future managers including those who will work with company HR, according to the programs in specialties “Management”, “Management of organizations and administration” (Ukraine), “Management and business administration”, “Management and public administration” (China) and their offer to applicants by 5-top universities of Ukraine and People’s Republic of China with the simultaneous absence of special

- educational components, which contribute to the formation of psychological and pedagogical competence of HR-managers;
- the provision of educational programs in the specialty “HR-management” by the Faculties of Economics and Management (experience of Ukraine and China), as well as Faculties of Management and Administration, Faculties of Public Administration, Faculties of Social Sciences (experience of China) in higher education institutions;
 - the use of various mechanisms for the formation of separate components of psychological and pedagogical competence of future HR-managers: emphasizing the study of individual educational components in Psychology or Pedagogy as well as integration of knowledge from Psychology and Pedagogy into the content of professional courses, but psychological and pedagogical competence (as an integrative feature, which includes knowledge and skills in the field of psychology and pedagogy, necessary for the organization of continuous development as well as wellbeing of the company’s employees, contributes to ensuring the efficiency of professional activity in general and solving complex problems in non-standard situations of the professional environment, as well as inclinations, orientations and strategies for the development of one’s own general and professional personal culture, deepening and accumulation of experience in the field of HR management) is not formed.

The performed analysis shows that the formation of psychological and pedagogical competence at the level of initial professional training of HR-managers is insufficient, it does not differ in systematicity aimed at the formation of its individual components, which justifies the need for its formation in the process of corporate training organization.

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